

MECHANISM FOR TRAINING CADETS IN BELT WRESTLING
BASED ON A CLUSTER APPROACH

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Abstract. This article talks about the mechanisms of training cadets in belt wrestling based on the cluster approach in military educational institutions.

Key words: militarized educational institutions, sport, cluster, belt wrestling, cadets.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada xarbiylashtirilgan ta'lim muassasalarida klaster yondashuv asosida kursantlarni belbog'li kurashga o'rgatish mexanizmlari haqida so'z yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: xarbiylashtirilgan ta'lim muassasalari, sport, klaster, belbog'li kurash, kursantlar.

Абстракт. В данной статье говорится о механизмах обучения курсантов борьбе на поясах на основе кластерного подхода в военно-учебных заведениях.

Ключевые слова: военизированные учебные заведения, спорт, кластер, борьба на поясах, курсанты.

From the day Uzbekistan gained independence, attention to the development and improvement of the national characteristics of physical education and sports has increased. A number of Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, government decisions are aimed at raising a healthy generation. As a result, the development of national sports among the youth of our country has risen to high levels. One of the Uzbek national sports is belt wrestling. It is widespread

in the Fergana Valley and adjacent areas, in the Tashkent region. Since time immemorial, belt wrestling competitions have been organized at public elections and weddings. Wrestlers such as Ahmed the wrestler, who did not touch the ground in these competitions, added to the glory of our country.

After our country gained independence, our values, including national sports and folk games, are being restored. It should be noted that it is important to notice its subtleties in oriental one-on-one wrestling, especially in belt wrestling. Its methods will delight any fan. It is important that these methods are performed by wrestlers with both hands tied (wrestlers' hands should not be detached from the belt).

He has set himself the goal of enriching the methods of "belt wrestling" and gradually bringing it to the international arena. He himself was engaged in this type of national struggle for several years. He won several times in international competitions dedicated to the memory of famous wrestlers Ahmed, Askar, Karatoy, Heroes of Labor Buzruk Ota and Mannop Jalolov, as well as in the championships of our republic.

A number of works are being carried out to further improve the scientific-based practical and methodological theory of belt wrestling to wrestlers on all continents and to ensure its development provided remains a fair, humane exercise. After all, struggle is a symbol of the self that comes from human nature.

Wrestling is one of the oldest sports and has a very interesting and bright history. For many thousands of years, ancient man has passed a difficult path from instinctive attack and defense actions to coordinated actions close to modern fighting methods.

Uzbek wrestling was born in ancient times and it is reflected in a large number of historical monuments.

During the archaeological excavations conducted in the territory of present-day Uzbekistan, ancient paintings depicting the methods of fighting, which include the methods of peaceful settlement of disputes, as well as the capture of the enemy, were found. It is worth mentioning that before the competitions, exercises were performed, including throws, jumps, and demonstration of strength. They served as a means of warming up the opponents before the competition. Wrestlers grabbed each other's leather belts or different parts of their upper clothes and started fighting. When performing the method of throwing the opponent to the ground, great attention is paid to the work of the legs and the method of striking.

In the peoples living in the territory of Uzbekistan, the competition continued until the first throw. These competitions were held to the sound of national music and the winner of the competition was highly respected by the people.

Belt wrestling differs from other sports due to the many and varied technical movements of the athlete.

The principles of training belt wrestlers are the general-theoretical principles of training wrestlers and teaching methods.

The following principles are implemented in the training of belt wrestlers.

1. Pedagogical (didactic) principles (the principle of awareness and activity, the principle of demonstrability, the principle of regularity and sequence, the principle of comprehensibility and individualization).

2. Principles of improvement of sports skills (principle of strength and variability of skills, principle of compatibility and principle of joint conduct in a directed manner).

3. Principles of sports training (the principle of achieving the unity of general and special physical training, the principle of repetition and continuity of the training process, the principle of gradation, the principle of gradually increasing training loads).

The coach helps the wrestler to acquire special knowledge, skills and abilities quickly and effectively, while implementing the principles that represent the main laws of organizing the pedagogical process.

All principles are interrelated and complement each other. If one principle is not taken into account, none of the others can be fully implemented. High results can be achieved in the training of a belt wrestler only if they are used together.

However, the importance of the above-mentioned principles is not the same at different stages of the formation of a belt wrestler's sports training.

Pedagogical (didactic) principles are more important at the stage of primary training. As the skill of a belt wrestler increases, the importance of sportsmanship and the principles of sports training increases.

The essence of the principle of demonstrability is the maximum use of athlete analyzers to solve training tasks in belt wrestling. The principle of demonstrability is based on the fact that the acquisition of movement skills depends on perception through the senses. It represents the need to ensure the wrestler's vision, movement and other ideas about the movement being studied. Receptive types are distinguished - visual, motor and acoustic. These three types are combined in different people and each of them can be more dominant. It is necessary for the coach to know which triggers are perceived more by this or that student. This helps him to effectively implement the principle of demonstration.

Demonstration of techniques in training with belt wrestlers serves as a basis for training and improvement. A coach can demonstrate a technique through videos, photos, posters, or show it with an athlete, orally, perform the technique on his or her own athlete, or have the athlete perform the technique on his or her own. It is part of this principle to perform on someone else. In order to understand this principle well, it is often necessary to involve the senses. Practical tools are used in the application of specific pedagogical issues (with practical tools) sequentially and separately in connection with each other.

Only after the participants have a correct idea about the method, their attention should be directed to important details, because the technique of performing the method will depend on it.

The trainer should demonstrate the method several times and it is very important that the trainees can see it from different angles.

Also, it is more effective to use a holistic method of demonstrating the method when working with teenagers. In this case, the main task is facilitated by a system of approximation and preparatory exercises.

In order to increase the effectiveness of training with belt wrestlers, the coach should use visual aids as much as possible to help create an idea of the studied method or its main details.

The principle of comprehensibility and individualization is to take into account the group, age-specific and individual differences of belt wrestlers when choosing optimal loads in the training process.

If the coach knows well the work activities, studies, living conditions and mental characteristics of the wrestlers, he can choose a reasonable method of training with them.

Belt wrestling classes for athletes of different ages and physical fitness are stratified by the composition of the coach and groups of athletes of different training, the training material for each it is necessary to select different types and determine the physical loads allowed in training.

What is easy for a skilled belt wrestler is not always easy for a novice athlete. In a state of high training, a wrestler with different belts can easily carry a large load, but this load can be heavy for an untrained or young athlete.

If the coach gives complex technical and tactical tasks to young wrestlers in pursuit of high sports results, it will be difficult for the young wrestler and may lead to loss of self-confidence and in some cases, injury. Therefore, the coach should choose and regulate the exercises in such a way that the load should match

the abilities of the participants. Learning material can be mastered only when it is understandable to athletes. This means overcoming difficulties that require effort. The study of the effect of training loads on the body of young belt wrestlers shows that if the training load does not match the capabilities of the trainees, in a number of cases, nervous disorders occur in their health.

The principle of comprehensibility and individualization requires that, when gathering groups of trainers, they should select athletes of approximately the same height, experience in sports and the level of training.

Control exercises and tests are important in choosing the right training groups. Based on the indicators he can get from his trainees as a result of accepting the standard requirements, as well as based on their level of special physical fitness, the coach makes adjustments to the material of the training program. Defines the limits of the size and content, as well as future goals and ways to achieve them.

The coach must follow the general principles of teaching and training, taking into account the age characteristics, skills and training level, and organize the training process in such a way that it is necessary to individualize the training of athletes as much as possible. The importance of individualized training increases (especially) in the stage of formation of high sports skills of a belt wrestler.

It is known that in a group of belt wrestlers of the same age, qualification and initial training, two athletes with absolutely identical indicators do not meet. Therefore, one of the main tasks of the trainer is to strictly individualize the training process of each belt wrestler as early as possible.

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